

EVOLUTION OF EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE IN PRODUCT DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

To clarify the relationship between design and emotion, this paper attempted to apply the 'Evolution of Emotional Development (EED)' into Desmet's clarification of Product Emotion (CPE) Model. To more clearly identify the relationship between Versions in EED and Desmet's CPE, this paper comes up with the figure that demonstrates the relationship. Version 3 in EED can be divided into social and interest emotions in Desmet's model. Users can have emotional satisfaction either from interaction with other users (social emotions) or from interaction with products (interest emotions).

Keywords: Emotional experience, emotional satisfaction, mate design, emotion, product design

RESEARCH BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Recently, smart machines such as robots living with human beings could be possible only in the movies. Regardless of the high robotic technology, there is a limit that a robot can have an emotional exchange with human beings. A number of products have recently had overcome the limitation of carrying out not just the initially programmed, but capable of meeting the aesthetic needs, and even reaching to a state of sharing/mixing emotions with human beings.

In this paper, design in product is discussed in three distinct development steps that enhances along with the increase of its versions. The final version so termed Ver3.0 is mainly discussed in this paper. This version can be regarded as mate design; design that interacts emotional feelings between products and human beings.

EVOLUTION OF EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERISTICS

The word design is comprised of two aspects, one is function-based or functional design and the other is emotion based or emotional design. The main difference between both designs above is that the emotional design provides overall aesthetic appreciations through the five senses of human beings. Meanwhile, functional design mainly deals with single senses/needs. Emotional design is, beyond the mere joy from the sight and audio. It fulfills the user's mental satisfaction through emotional interactions. The development of emotional design, depending on its characteristics, can be categorized into three versions below.

Features	Ver	Ver 1.0	Ver 2.0	Ver 3.0
Functional Satisfaction				
Aesthetical Satisfaction				
Emotional Satisfaction				

Table 1 Emotional Design Development Characteristic

(1) Ver 1.0 : Functional design.

Functional design is mainly to fulfill user needs by easing their ordinary works such as chores. Since the objects are mainly intended to focus on functional base, design is not considered highly important in this step. Examples in this version include the very first prototype of in-house-machines such as vacuum cleaner, dish washer and other household products.

(2) Ver 2.0 : Aesthetic design.

In Ver 2.0, functionally-designed products in Version 1.0 have been improved both in its outlook and functions. Not only its function has been diversified into more options but the design has improved a lot, adding enjoyment while using the product. However, a majority of the products in Ver 2.0 have been combined with design in abrupt manners that many bugs occurred as well as requiring users to be highly knowledgeable about objects before use.

(3) Ver 3.0 : Emotionally Rewarding Design

In this stage, products have certainly been enhanced in its design and smartness to overcome defects in ver 2.0 product can read/understand user's thoughts and intentions are delivered to design product and may accordingly get responses. Design examples in Ver 3.0 include a number of current gadgets that can be defined as smart. Since designed products in this stage are thought to interact with its user, we would like to call it as 'mate design'.

Ver3.0. has encouraged significant changes in our life style and society as a whole, according to the following examples

Figure2 Different types of chair located on the Evolution of Emotional Design (EED) Chart

In the charts above, ver3.0 in products can be explained by three chairs with significantly different designs. Two axes above represent emotion and function. Five different chairs from A to E are positioned above reflecting their emotional and functional levels. Ver 3.0, the focus of this paper can be explained by three chairs in the figure above. Chair C represents its relatively more emotional aspects, and chair D is a reflection of our nostalgia in our childhood. Chair E that is at least partly concerned with eco-friendliness satisfies both emotional and functional needs.

Figure1 Evolution of Emotional Design (EED) Chart

CURRENT STAGE OF EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Through the example shown above, we can notice that advances into ver 3.0 has actually 'progressed' from what it had been, not really a change. Before emotional exchange were to be accomplished, our life took in a form where user centers between coexistence of electronic products, objects and space, which we would like to name as electronic mates; prototype of ver3.0 products. However with the transgression of sympathetic functions, distance and hierarchy like system between electronic mates and human will keep evolving, thus uplifting emotional relationships between both, making them in more horizontal form.

Actually this kind of variance is already being witnessed from several SF movies. From a movie 'Iron

man', iron man is the hero of the movie live in ver3.0 space which helps him throughout working by assisting iron man, with ver 3.0mates who helps him out in working as well as being good friend. From the steps that Iron man turns out a real hero, 'The iron man' ver3.0 space and products do not simply coexist at a horizontal state but it even rises to the high state. Actually in our daily life, the experiment of evolution in ver 3.0 space has been tested assiduously by using 'kitchen' as a model. Recently 'Mino Laboratory' of Kyoto University has announced a smart-kitchen system that had a system of aiding it's user by detecting user behaviors in cooking and letting kitchen tools aid the users by adapting it.

Figure3 Smart kitchen by Mino Laboratory [Source from : <http://www.imel1.kuis.kyoto-u.ac.jp/en/research/skitchen.html>]

DEVELOPMENT DESMET'S CLASSIFICATION OF PRODUCT EMOTIONS

Desmet (2007) made an attempt to suggest a framework that includes all possible affective experiences involved in actual human-product interaction. The above interaction covers instrumental and non-instrumental interaction, and even non-physical interaction. The above experiences can be distinguished into three distinct levels of product experiences that include aesthetic experience, experiencing of meaning, and emotional experience. From the cognitive perspective of emotion, based on Frijda (1986), Desmet (2003) defined emotions related to a product as an appraisal process in which the individual appraises the product as (potentially) harming or favoring one or several of that person's concerns [1, 5]. Emotional response is not just concerned with styling. It is more about affluent emotions that cover both pleasant and unpleasant emotions. Multiple emotions can be involved in the

process [1, 2]. These emotions include surprise, instrumental, aesthetic, social and interest.

Figure4 Classification of Product Emotions [1]

CONCLUSION

To clarify the relationship between design and emotion, this paper made an attempt to apply the 'Evolution of Emotional Development (EED)' into Desmet's Clarification of Product Emotion (CPE) Model. To more clearly deliver the relationship between Versions 1 to 3 in EED and Desmet's CPE, this paper comes up with the figure below. Version 3 in EED can be divided into Social and interest emotions in Desmet's model. Users can have emotional satisfaction either from interaction with other users (social emotions) or from interaction with products (interest emotions).

Figure5 Evolution of Emotional Design (EED) & Clarification of Product Emotion (CPE)

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